

COACHING – A NEW TECHNIQUE OF TEACHER TRAINING

Dr. Vijaya Patil

Asso. Professor School of Education

Y.C.M.O.U Nashik

Introduction:-

Transfer refers to the effect of learning one kind of material or skill or the ability to learn something new. The newly acquired skills must be transferred when it is transferred into one's active teaching repertoire. The condition of classroom are sufficiently different from training situation that one can not simply walk from the training session into the classroom with the skill completely ready for use. The skills have to be changed to fit classroom conditions. This is truer in the case of unfamiliar skill. To master a new teaching strategy, teacher needs to develop mastery in the skills or strategies. This can be accomplished in training setting. Then the teachers need to acquire executive control over it including ability to use it appropriately and to adopt it into classroom setting (Joyce, B & Showers 1988) therefore believe that transfer of skills is actually a new set of learning. The mastery of the new strategy that the distinction between horizontal and vertical transfer becomes important.

Horizontal and vertical Transfer:

Horizontal transfer refers to conditions in which a skill can be shifted directly from the training situation on order to solve problems. Vertical transfer refers to conditions in which the new skill cannot be used to solve problems unless it is adopted to fit the conditions of the workplace-that is, an extension of learning is regard before problems can be solved effectively. Vertical transfer is more likely when the context of training and the conditions of the workplace are

different, a given skill is different from one's exact repertoire and does not fit easily into it or additional understanding is needed to achieve executive control over the skills. When the skill just 'slides' from the training place to workplace, that is horizontal process, when additional learning is required to transfer the skill, that is vertical process. An important factor is the degree to which the new skill disrupts exact patterns of performance. The greater the degree to which a new skill fits into already familiar patterns, the less adjustment is needed.

Developing Executive Control:

The conditions of performance can be divided into two categories-those in which the circumstances of performance demand the utilization of the skills and those in which the skills are brought into play a consequence of a judgement made by the performer. In other words, a shifting and changing scene of events is reduced as much as possible to sets of operation that can be brought into play when the appropriate cues appear in the environment. General principles are formulated and taught so as to activate the skills.

"Executive control consists of understanding the purpose and rationale of the skill and knowing how to adopt it to students, apply it to subject matter, modify or create instructional materials attendant to its use, organize students to use it, and blend it with other instructional approaches to develop a smooth and powerful whole".

The Process of Coaching:

Setting up arrangements for trainees to develop a self help community to provide coaching is essential if transfer is to be achieved. Ideally, "Coaching teams" are developed during training. Coaching teams who regularly observe one another's teaching and provide helpful information, feedback and so forth. In the development of a "Coaching environment" in which all personnel see

themselves as one another's coaches. Coaching involves four major functions:

1. the provision of companionship
2. the provision of technical feedback
3. the analysis of application
4. adaptation to the students

1 . The provision of companionship:

Its first function is to provide interchange with another human being over a difficult process. The coaching relationship results in the possibility of mutual reflection, the checking of perceptions, the sharing of frustrations and successes, and the informal thinking through of mutual problems. Two people, watching each other try a new model of teaching for the first time. Will find much to talk about companionship provides reassurance that the problems are normal. Both find that their habitual and automatic teaching patterns create awkwardness when they practice the new procedures. Concentrating on unfamiliar moves and ideas, they forget essential little odds and ends. It enhances the quality of the experience. It is a lot more pleasurable to share a new thing than to do it in isolation.

2. The Provision of technical feedback:

Team members learn to provide feedback to one another as they practice their new model of teaching. They point out omissions, examine how materials are arranged, and check to see whether all parts of the teaching strategy have been brought together, and so on. "Technical" feedback helps ensure that growth continues through practice in the classroom. The pressures of the context tend to diffuse the teaching experience and draw attention away from the new teaching strategy. The provision of technical feedback helps keep the of the teacher on the business of perfecting skills, polishing them, and working thorough problem

areas. The coaching partner has the privilege of seeing a number of trials of the new model by another skill teacher. Ideas about how to use the models are also collected through observation. Coaching team can receive feedback vicariously while watching others and they will also produce a number of fine practices that constitute further demonstration and from which they can obtain ideas for maximizing their use of the model.

3. Analysis of application: Extending executive control:-

Among the most important thing one learns during the transfer period are when to use a new model appropriately and what will be achieve by doing so selecting the right occasions to use a teaching strategy is not as easy as it sounds. Nearly everyone needs help in learning to pick the right spot unfamiliar teaching processes also appear to have less certain outcomes than to he familiar ones. During raining, the coaching teams needs to spend a considerable amount of time examining curriculum materials and plans and practicing the application of the application of the model they will be using later than as the process of transfer begins, practice in the classroom is in the classroom is intensified with closer and closer attention given to appropriate use.

4. Adaptation to the Students:

Successful teaching requires successful student response. Teacher are familiar with the task of teaching students how to engage in common instructional activities. A model that is new to a group of students however will cause them trouble. They will need to learn new skill and to become acquainted with what is expected of them, how to fulfil the task demands of the new methods and how to gauge their own progress. Adaptation to the students is relatively difficult and usually requires a lot of direct assistance and companionship.

One of the major functions of the coach is to help the “playas” to “read” the responses of the students so that the right decision are made about what skill

training is needed and how to adapt the model. Successful use of a new method requires practice. One of the principal jobs of the coaching team then is to help its members feel good about themselves during the early trials. Coaching reduces the isolations and offers genuine support. On practical basis most coaching should be done by teams of teachers working together to study new approaches to teaching and to polish their existing teaching skills. But if only as a matter of logistics, teachers are closer to one another and in an excellent position to do most of the coaching necessary. Joyce and Showers have reviewed training studies among of skill acquisition and they found that only in those studies where training include coaching component the transfer had acquired. Creeemen B.P.M. and Hoeben W. Th.J.G. Gerry. J. Reezight used the concept of coating for transfer of skills required for implementation new curriculum material and the results of their study were fairly favourable.

Coaching in Y. C. M. O. U. B. Ed Programme-

Y.C.M.O.U. has a component of coaching in its B. Ed programme meant for in-service teachers. It was used by the university in order to ensure transfer of training of newly acquired non routine teaching methods such as

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|--------------------------------|---------------------------|
| 1. Communication Approach | 2. Journey method |
| 3. Problem solving | 4. Inductive-Deductive |
| 5. Dramatization | 6. Lecture method |
| 7. Discussion | 8. Problem solving method |
| 9. Minimum competence teaching | |

The university developed elaborate coaching procedure. After the practice the students from a group of two consider the geographical vicinity. The centre co-ordinator, Directors help the students in case of difficulties. The students interact frequently in order to know each other and exchange the information of

newly acquired teaching methods. Lesson observation is decided other discussion. Feedback regarding the errors in teaching is provided after observation of the actual lesson. Individual as well as combined report is submitted to the study centre at the end. The scheme is presented in the following flowchart-

Scheme of Coaching in YCMOU

Knowing each others, background of education, family workplace, attitude, purpose doing in B. Ed, difficulties and problems in practical work.

** Identifying appropriate units for teaching preparing of four lessons.

*** Discussing each other methods, observing lessons, giving feedback.

After coaching exercise the student teachers submit report of the work done in

the capacity of student teacher and capacity of coach. The report highlights the difficulties in transferring the new teaching methods in routine teaching. The scheme has been very recently introduced. The researcher conducted study of the scheme which is still in progress. The effectiveness of scheme in its early stage is judged on the basis of the responds by the participants in interview from Nasik centre for this purpose. The analyses of data gather are presented in the section to follow

Section-1- Purpose of Coaching

There was only one question related to clarity of purpose of coaching. The data related to same in presented.

Q.1 What is coaching? What is the objectives of coaching?

Table No.1

No.	Feedback	No. of Students	%
1.	A+C	03	12.5
2.	A+B	04	16.66
3.	A+B+C	10	41.66
4.	A+D	01	4.16
5.	A+B+C+E	01	4.16
6.	B+C	03	12.5
7.	B+C+E	01	4.16
8.	C+D	01	4.16

- A) Partner's feedback
- B) Friendly co-operation
- C) Progress in teaching
- D) Transfer in teaching
- E) Other

Observation-& Interpretation:

1. Partner's feedback 2. Friendly co-operation 3. Progress in teaching 4. Transfer in teaching are the major purpose of according to majority of the

students 75%. The main purpose has not appealed to the students. It means that purpose of transfer is not clear to students.

Finding- Coaching scheme does not communicate the main purpose of the scheme

Section -2 Effectiveness of Coaching

Three questions were related to effectiveness of coaching. Two were related to feedback utilization and one to its effectiveness in transfer of teaching.

Table No.2

Q.2 Are the teaching methods taught to your transferred in your teaching?

	Yes	No	Partially	Undecided
No. of Students	13	4	7	-
Percentages	54.16	16.66	29.16	-

Observation & Interpretation:

More than 50% student teachers agreed that transfer of teaching has occurred in their teaching. Only 16% student teachers say that transfer of training has not occurred because of coaching.

Finding: Coaching ensures transfer fully or partially.

Table No.3

Q.3 Can feedback really help for effective teaching?

	Feedback Helps	Feedback does not help	Feedback Partially helps
No. of students	24	-	-
Percentage	100	-	-

Observation & Interpretation:

Almost of all students in unanimously agreed that feedback has helped in improving their teaching.

Finding: Coaching improved feedback giving and receiving activities which ultimately improves their teaching.

Table No.4

Q.4 How is the feedback useful for your teaching?

	a	b	c	d	E
No of Students	6	3	9	2	4
Percentages	2.5	12.5	37.5	8.3	16.66

- A) Making appropriate changes in teaching.
- B) Change in preparation.
- C) Changes in teaching skills
- D) Emotional change
- E) Other

Observation & Interpretation: 37 % students think that the feedback is useful for changing in teaching skills. 25% students think that the feedback is useful for making appropriate changes in teaching methods. 12% students think that feedback is useful for to changing preparation 8.3% students think that feedback is useful for to emotional change.

Finding: Feedback is useful for making changes in teaching in teaching methods and skills.

Table no. 5

Q.5 Did u face the Problems in coaching ?

	Yes	No	Partially	Undecided
No. of Students	4	20	-	-
Percentages	16.66	80.16	-	-

Observation & Interpretation:

Most of the students did not face problems in coaching.

Finding: Coaching training is effective.

Conclusion:

On the basis of responses it can be said that coaching is effective in ensuring transfer of training and improving teaching. There are no major difficulties in incorporation scheme in teacher training.

Recommendations

- 1) There is a need to underline the main purpose of coaching in the orientation.
- 2) Compatibility should be ensured by keeping the same medium of instruction and the same level of teaching while deciding the partners.
- 3) As far as possible it should be seen that the partner should be in geographical vicinity.

Future Research:

For the future research few topics can be suggested.

- 1) Effectiveness of coaching should be studied in a more systematic way.
- 2) In-depth studies on various aspects of coaching can be also undertaken. The aspects may be observation, feedback, emotional changes, attitudes and performance changes.

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